

THE METHODS AND MEANS OF CREATING HUMOR IN UZBEK CHILDREN LITERATURE

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Abstract. This article analyses the poetic image, artistic details, and situation that cause laughter, words, and concepts in humorous poems must have a gradual development through the evolution of thinking with the renewal of space and time, object and subject.

Keywords: humor, laughter, comic, psychology, anecdote, theme, plot, idea, symbol, evolution, rhyme, imitation words.

At the same time, various methods and means of creating humor can be observed in a number of poet's poems. We will try to classify them as follows:

1. Through the creative stylization of jokes typical of children's folklore:

Farhod cho'milar // Suvga ko'milar.

Tilini chiqarib // Ermaklar Mirsharif:

"Farhod – paroxod // Farhod – paroxod..."

Ter to'kib sharros // Suv tashir Parvoz.

Tilini chiqarib // Ermaklar Mirsharif:

«Parvoz – parovoz // Parvoz – parovoz...»

Pranks are a special genre in children's folklore. There are tons of jokes woven according to his name and nature. (For example: Safiya safon, Boshiga chopon, To'y boradi, Bedasturxon; yoki: Juma jumaloq, Xandakka yumaloq, Xandakni pechak bosdi, Jumani chesak bosdi. Yana: Ra'no, Ra'no ranichka, Oyog'iga tapichka, Tapichkasi g'ichillaydi, Ra'noxonim achchiqlaydi kabi) In the humorous poem of A. Obidjon renews the object of laughter by calling him "Mirsharif an idler". That is, the reason for the nickname is not Farhad and Parvaz, but Mirsharif's idleness. He is being laughed at for mocking his friends who worked hard and trained by bathing.

1. Through children's games and creating scenery. The poem "Kolxoz bog'ida" (In the collective farm garden) depicts the scene of the children's attack by the army. Only at the end of the poem, "We will trample the garden, we will eat apples." Shouting and screaming. If the watchman comes, the whistle blows, the whistle blows, our retreat is creaking" sentences are just a game of the children who have fallen into the collective farm garden, their childhood fun, and they share a smile with both adults and children.

2. Based on the image of a unique situation.

In one of the poet's poems in this direction, it is clear that Botirvoy befriended a warm and soft woolen sock last winter, and until this winter he wrote a dirge, repenting that his "friend" was unfortunately eaten by a mouse. In the poem, Botirvoy's friendship with a woolen sock was funny, but now it is even more funny that that "friend" was eaten by a mouse. Also, in the poem "Parishonhotir" (Thoughtful) Jamil takes off his clothes to take a bath and throws his clothes into the water instead of himself.

3. By choosing a title.

4. Qumursqavoy

Topib uvoq,

Terga botib

Tortdi uzoq.

Chumchuq kelib

Sekingina,

Yutdi-qo'ydi

Tekingina.

If the title of this poem is not "Tekinxo'r", then a simple scene is considered a poem. However, because gluttony is an undesirable vice, a bad habit, the sparrow's act is ridiculed. Many of the poet's poems acquire a deep meaning, an artistic and aesthetic task, just by their title.

5. Humorous words through terms.

The title of the poet's poems "Hazilkash" (Humorous), "Masqaraboz bola" (Clown boy) are also keywords of humor. Clowns in particular cause laughter as soon as they appear. And his task is to make people laugh at their stupid behavior and habits. It even shows the type of laugh:

Katta qizil burunli

Qiziqchiman, bilasiz.

Aybingizni gapirsam,

Xafa bo'lmay kulasiz,

Vax-xax-xa.

Gapirishdan iymangan

Olsin mening o'rnimni.

Qarzga berib turaman

Katta qizil burnimni,

Vax-xax-xa.

At this point, it is appropriate to justify how many different types of laughter there are in our mother tongue through the story of the great poet A. Oripov: "Italians asked me: 'Is the strength and richness of the Uzbek language enough to translate Alighieri Dante's "Divine Comedy"?!' I explained to them how wide the possibilities of our language are and, of course, they don't know the possibilities of this language. The richness of any language is related to the synonyms of the words in it. I asked the Italians: - Tell me, how many different names for the wind do you have? They said two or three words. Then I listed them as wind, storm, hurricane... And finally, relying on our grandfather Alisher Navoi's work "Muhokamatul Lug'otayn", I asked: "How many types of crying do you have?" I said, for example, we cry 19 different ways. To cry, to roar, to squeeze, to complain, to moan, to steal, to scream... I explained that each of these words gives a different situation. Then they recognized the strength, power of expression and possibility of our language. In fact, one can ask how many different kinds of laughter we have. Laughter technique is a separate psychological state, most of them are directly related to words and expression, state. For example, laughing out loud (this kind of laughter is heard at large playgrounds and shows when you hear askiya, payrov), wah-haha-ha - it can be said that it is the innocent laughter of a person who has nothing in his heart. When you laugh hi-hi-hi-hi, your sarcasm is in the priority. In addition, the lexical meanings of laugh, smile, grin, giggle, etc., although they are very close to each other, differ according to the degree of gradualness, positive, negative, and emotional tone. Taking into account that humor in children's poetry has a positive meaning, it is characterized by the words smile, holler, giggle, squeal, giggle, as well as hearty laugh, shrill laugh, shout out laugh, hard laugh, laugh inside. While there are more than ten different types of laughter, five or six of them appear as a product of pure and sincere humor in children's literature. So, in many poems, the very appearance of these words causes laughter.

6. Creating humor by reversing events in the plot of the work.

In most of Anvar Obidjon's humorous poems, life events are reversed. For example, by reading the poet's poem "The Messenger", the scene of the market comes before our eyes. But this market has an antique trade like no other. The lyrical hero shouts, typical of overbearing merchants: "I sell new things, old things too. Guys, hurry up, there is very little left. Don't ask for the price, it's cheaper than balloon. For true news sweets, for lies cheese. I'll exchange the new one without the bran. The old saying - empty walnuts, or soap..." is interesting. And now his messages are also very old-fashioned, very opposite to the reality of

life, or very funny: I heard this in the morning, the latest news: a pigeon ate an eagle in a dream. In the same way, the rabbit covers the skin of the tiger, the fox gives the wolf a cock, the donkey laughs at the bear as illiterate, the camel complains to the doctor lion that a moth has fallen on his precious skin, and the doctor rubs his skin and examines it for a long time. These are sure to make kids and adults laugh. In addition to the many artistic and stylistic tools that provide the humorous features of the poem, the ironic content, and the interpretation of figurative and allegorical images leads the modern reader to think. It is the market trade, the selling of falsehoods, that makes one understand how deceptions resemble the reality of life. Every creature, including human beings, is weak. In fact, this is the law of living of animals. But unfortunately, humanity has already been infected. Therefore, everyone dreams that the opposite of this law of life will happen. In particular, children think about it both in their dreams and in their dreams. The poet realizes this fantasy in the poem, as he deeply understands this psychological state of children. This is the reason for children's joy and laughter. They are ready to buy such "messages".

This aspect is clearly reflected in A. Obidjon's poem "In the Hospital of Excusers". In this case, the excuses of animals really surprise the readers: because the doctor said that the rabbit was bitten by a wolf fly, the bear said that Olmakhon hit him with a nut, the goat said that an ant stuck its claw in my eye, the beetle crushed the dog's leg, the lion kicked the horse with a sledgehammer, He complains that the Ox was beaten by a Grasshopper, and the Rhinoceros was bitten by a predatory Ant, and the hospital is overcrowded. The lion also sleeps in a separate room, and only the donkey works without an excuse.

As it can be seen all the opposite events can happen, that is, it is clear that small insects can get stuck in the clutches of strong animals, under their feet, and get injured. The poet creates laughter by deliberately switching their place. Children who know the verbs and characteristics of the mentioned animals laugh with pleasure at the poet's findings and feel sorry for a single donkey. At the same time, they laugh at his inability to make excuses for being "simple". Even so, it means a renewed artistic aesthetic function of humor. It is understood that the goal can be achieved not only with hard work but also with intelligence and determination. That is, there is also a symbol of the people who are turning into black workers due to poverty, wandering, and lack of education.

7. Humorous poems created using praise

A. Obidjon's poems are based on praises. Although these praises are about animals, animal foods are about humans. This is the basis of laughter. It may not

be interesting if the poet praises the Rhinoceros for drinking only a hundred bunches of alfalfa or a hundred buckets of water, but in the poem "Ishtahangdan o'rgildim "(I'm Tired of your Appetite) the lazy Rhinoceros walks into the kitchen with the lyrical hero. Since he ate fifty-five loaves of bread, six bags of cucumbers, forty buckets of soup, ninety eggs, one hundred glasses of compote, and seventy plates of meat soup, he will not have lunch.

Thus, in modern children's poetry, the artistic and aesthetic tasks of humor are not to expose and ridicule the misbehavior and character flaws of schoolchildren, children, but to pay more attention to the problems related to the changes in the thinking of society and social development, along with the changes in the mentality of the young generation. It turns into an aesthetic principle, like the growth of legal consciousness, and shows that it created the principle of gradual development.

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